

MEASUREMENT OF THE INTERNAL STRAIN DISTRIBUTION IN A REINFORCED RUBBER-MATRIX COMPOSITE USING DIGITAL VOLUME CORRELATION

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ABSTRACT

The internal strain distribution of a rubber-matrix composite specimen, reinforced with nylon cords and subjected to a tensile load was measured using the volumetric strain measurement technique known as Digital Volume Correlation (DVC) and modeled using a specialized finite element method. Similar to Digital Image Correlation (DIC) the DVC method uses a high-contrast pattern to accurately extract motion vectors from volumetric images in the loaded and unloaded configuration and the strain distribution can then be derived from the displacement vector fields. Unlike the surface measurement technique DIC, DVC permits the quantification of strain distributions throughout the entire volume of the specimen. The specimen used for this study was molded using silicone rubber (Momentive RTV-664) infused with glass micro-beads and voids to provide an internal pattern of high contrast for the strain measurement technique. The rubber was reinforced with 3.0 mm nylon cords in a [45/90/45] manner. A baseline study was conducted to assess whether the imaging process introduces any systematic error to the measurements. This study consisted of rigid body translations and rotations of the sample without applying any load. The sample was then loaded in tension and volumetric images were taken under load. All volumetric image sets were then processed using the Vic-Volume software from Correlated Solutions, Inc.

The specimen was also modeled using a specialized textile finite element code developed within the Air Force Research Laboratory. This code allows the user to generate stress analysis models of highly complex textile composites. Material properties and reinforcement locations were modeled approximately with respect to the actual specimen. A comparison between the strain distribution obtained from finite element modeling and the volumetric correlation measurements is presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

The digital image correlation (DIC) technique has found widespread acceptance in the experimental mechanics community over the recent years due to its ease of use, high spatial resolution and high accuracy. However, the two- and three-dimensional DIC techniques are limited to the evaluation of deformation on the surface only. Historically, deformation measurements on the interior have been limited to embedded sensors such as fiber-optic strain sensors which provide only very sparse information and may alter the behavior of the material. In recent years, the DIC method has been extended to interior measurements using volumetric images acquired by tomography. The technique, known as Digital Volume Correlation (DVC) or Volumetric Digital Image Correlation (VDIC), was first demonstrated for solid mechanics applications by Bay [1] in 1999 and later improved by Smith [2]. In their pioneering work, Bay and his colleagues used X-ray micro-computed tomography (μ CT) to acquire volumetric image sets of a biological bone specimen before and during mechanical loading. Using a direct extension of two-dimensional DIC concepts [3], they performed DVC on the high contrast internal images of the bone structure to measure full-volume deformation fields during mechanical loading, confirming that the DIC technique developed previously could be directly extended to process 3D volumetric image sets. The DVC technique has the potential to permit researchers to directly measure deformation throughout the volume of a specimen, possibly identifying locations of critical behavior. This holds great promise for applications in the aerospace fields, where the use of composite materials is becoming more prevalent. The common feature most composite materials exhibit is the complexity of the distribution of stresses and strains during service due to the large disparity in constituent material properties, especially with respect to interlaminar behavior in laminates or between tows in textile composites. The availability of dense deformation data on the interior of composite structures has the potential to increase our understanding of the complex deformation behavior of these materials and to validate and improve our modeling capabilities.

In this article, a rubber-matrix composite specimen, reinforced with nylon cords, was investigated using the DVC technique both under load and no-load conditions. The no-load conditions served to assess bias and noise in the DVC technique, while the tensile load condition was used for comparison with results from a Finite Element Analysis (FEA) of the sample.

2 DVC AND MODELING TECHNIQUES

2.1 Volumetric Image Correlation

The DVC analysis was conducted using the Vic-Volume software package by Correlated Solutions, Inc. In brief, DVC analysis is conducted sub-volume by sub-volume, as shown schematically in Figure 1. For a sub-volume in the reference image set, the recorded intensity values in the undeformed sub-volume are optimally matched to a sub-volume in the deformed CT image by minimizing the following cost function, χ .

$$\chi = \sum_{n=1}^N \{I_{\text{def}}(\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{R}_n)) - I_{\text{ref}}(\mathbf{R}_n)\}^2 \quad (1)$$

where $N = m^3$ is the total number of voxels in a sub-volume and m is the number of voxels along one direction in a sub-volume; n is the designation for a specific voxel in a sub-volume; I_{ref} is the intensity at a voxel position $R(x,y,z)$ in the reference image; I_{def} is the intensity at the optimally located position in the deformed image, a is the vector mapping function that takes points in the undeformed image and transforms them to the deformed image and R_n is the three-dimensional position of the n -th point in the undeformed sub-volume image being analyzed.

The physical spatial region being imaged remains fixed throughout the CT scans for both undeformed and deformed specimen configurations. The material sub-volumes deform with the specimen and each sub-volume mapping functions a in Eq (1) is determined through an optimization process without requiring continuity in the deformations between sub-volumes. It is noted that for brevity, the description of the matching process has been simplified, and the actual implementation uses a more complex scheme, see Chapter 5 in [3] for details.

Figure 1: Schematic of Volumetric Image Correlation analysis.

2.2 Numerical Modeling Methods

The finite element analysis was carried out using two different modeling methods. The nylon cord morphology was assembled using a textile tow morphology toolset known as the *Virtual Textile Morphology Suite* (VTMS). This software code was also used as a pre-processor for a specialized finite element code known as the *Independent Mesh Method* (IMM), which resides within the *B-Spline Analysis Method* (BSAM). These software packages are research codes developed at the Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL).

VTMS is based on the multi-chain digital element method, as described in [4], which is formulated to simulate realistic textile tow morphologies. In this methodology, a tow is represented as a number of filaments where each filament is a digital chain. A digital chain is composed of many rod-elements, defined as “digital elements”, as shown in Figure 2. Rotational nodes connect rod elements. It is thus able to represent a 1D flexible physical entity with a fixed cross-section, such as a fiber. When a digital chain approaches another digital chain, contact between two digital chains can be represented by contact between nodes from two neighboring chains as shown in Figure 2. Each chain is assigned an initial tension, and the system is allowed to relax through a series of iterative solutions.

Figure 2: Schematic of a single digital chain (a) and two digital chains (b) interacting through a contact element.

The *Independent Mesh Method* (IMM) finite element code was developed to specifically address difficulties with analysis of complex textile composite materials. In the IMM, meshes for tows are generated from solid representations of the tows. Once obtained, these meshes are combined with an arbitrary mesh representing the matrix, with dimensions equal to the outer dimensions of the specimen. All meshes are developed independently of each other and connections between tows and matrix are applied by using a penalty method or cohesive zone interface. For a more detailed description of the method, we refer to [5].

3 SPECIMEN FABRICATION AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A rubber-matrix composite specimen, reinforced with nylon cords, was manufactured for examination with DVC. Three-strand twist nylon cord of approximately 2.3mm diameter was obtained. These were dipped into a primer solution intended to promote bonding to silicon rubber and then allowed to air dry. A cord reinforcement pattern was first established by drilling a series of 3mm holes around the perimeter of a 139.7mm diameter petri dish. Three layers of cords were threaded through the holes, resulting in a layered reinforcement pattern of $[90^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ]$, where the 90° layers consisted of 3 cords each and the 45° layer consisted of 9 cords as shown in Figure 3a. The holes around the petri dish perimeter were then sealed with tape. A sufficient amount of Momentive RTV-664 silicone was mixed thoroughly. Additionally, a small quantity of glass micro-beads, ranging in size

Figure 3: Specimen fabrication with (a) nylon cords suspended at various layers in a petri dish and (b) RTV-664 silicone rubber poured over cords and pin locations.

up to approximately 200 microns, was added to the silicon rubber mix. These beads and the distribution of voids throughout the rubber served as the high-contrast pattern for the subsequent DVC analysis. Two 7.94 mm pins were carefully positioned 101.6 mm apart along the intended centerline of the specimen. The rubber mixture was poured into the petri dish to a level of approximately 19.6 mm (Figure 3b). Cord layers were located at 5.64mm and 13.31 mm for the 90° layers and 9.22 mm for the 45° layer. Upon cure, the rubber was removed from the petri dish and cut with razor blades to a size of 38.1 mm in width using the pins as guides. The pins were then removed resulting in the specimen as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Final specimen configuration cut to a width of 38.1 mm. Note: cord ends have been circled for enhanced visibility, and coordinate origin is drawn as it is considered in the subsequent DVC and numerical analyses.

3.1 Baseline Tests

The application of the DIC method to image material acquired by instruments other than digital cameras has historically brought a lot of challenges with it. As the method's aim is the measurement of minuscule length changes, even small aberrations in the imaging process can have severe detrimental impact and result in large strain bias. This has been observed, e.g., in images obtained through scanning electron microscopy and atomic force microscopy, and even much simpler devices such as stereo microscopes. Common to all of these acquisition methods is that a strain bias is encoded in the images even under rigid body translation. This bias is either due to spatial or temporal distortions that require special calibration methods. In order to determine whether volumetric images obtained with the X-ray μ CT system are affected in a similar manner, a baseline study was conducted. The first test, which is typically failed by SEM imagery, was to repeatedly scan the sample without application of any translation or loading to assess whether there is any drift or instability in the scanning process. After the no-motion test, a series of translation tests was performed to assess whether there are any spatially varying distortions present in the image material. For the translation tests, the sample was moved by varying amounts in all three axes. All tests were carried out in a Nikon Metrology μ CT system. Figure 5 shows a magnified reconstructed slice near the mid-plane of the sample and a sectioned false-color region showing the nylon cords in grey and the rubber matrix in blue.

Figure 5: (a) Close-up near the mid-plane of the specimen and (b) sectioned μ CT image of the scanned portion of the specimen (axes for reference only).

3.2 Load Application

A simple load fixture suitable for insertion into an X-ray micro μ CT system was constructed. It consisted of a thick-walled cardboard tube with aluminum end caps. The end caps allowed the unit to be mounted to the μ CT rotation stage and contained hardware for attaching loading clevises. The specimen was loaded via 7.4mm pins inserted through the aluminum clevises. Displacement was applied through the turn of a nut on a threaded rod mounted to one of the clevises. A graphical visualization of the loaded specimen with the boundary conditions used for FEA is shown in Figure 6. Specimen rotation about the Y-axis was not restricted, and the load application method had potential to cause twist. This apparatus was inserted into a Nikon Metrology μ CT system, scanned at zero-load, and then scanned with approximately 6.5 mm of pin displacement. Each scan examined the central 50 mm of the specimen. After scanning, the two data sets were cropped to the region of mutual overlap, resulting in a common-scanned region of 47.8 mm in the Y-direction.

Figure 6: Graphical description of the applied displacements.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All volumetric images were analyzed using the Vic-Volume analysis code by Correlated Solutions, Inc. The subset size chosen was $31 \times 31 \times 31$ voxels with a spacing of 7 voxels in each direction between data points. For strain computation, a $5 \times 5 \times 5$ neighborhood was chosen to minimize smoothing. For the baseline tests, this resulted in approximately 160,000 data points per image set. The baseline tests showed only minor variations in mean strain and standard deviation between the different tests. Table 1 therefore only shows the worst case values for the normal strains and the highest value among the three shear strains. The confidence margin σ of the displacement estimates reported by the analysis code was approximately 0.002 voxels for all tests. This is significantly lower than what is typical in 2D and 3D image correlation because the three-dimensional sub-volume used for displacement analysis contains much more information than the two-dimensional subsets used in regular DIC. In all tests, the normal strain in the z-direction showed approximately twice the amount of bias than the other two directions and approximately 50% more noise. The cause of this increased noise is unclear and will be the subject of further investigation. The amount of bias present in the strain data is somewhat higher compared to typical 3D DIC tests, but acceptably low for a wide range of applications.

Quantity		Mean	Standard Deviation
σ	[voxel]	0.002	0.00037
ϵ_{xx}	$[\mu\epsilon]$	61	230
ϵ_{yy}	$[\mu\epsilon]$	75	220
ϵ_{zz}	$[\mu\epsilon]$	130	330
ϵ_{shear}	$[\mu\epsilon]$	18	200

Table 1: Bias and noise in different strain components. Worst values from all tests.

The volumetric images from the load tests were analyzed in the same manner as the images sets from the baseline tests. As the load fixture was not instrumented, boundary conditions for the FE model were determined by matching the average strain in the loading direction on the top and bottom surface of the region of interest. A detailed description of the FE model can be found in [6].

A comparison between the measured and modeled displacement fields on the outer faces of the region of interest is shown in Figure 7. The match in magnitude and distribution are quite close with the U component showing the greatest difference. Evidence of the influence of the nylon cords is clearly visible in both data sets. Twist and bending are also shown to be properly captured by the modeled boundary conditions and pin offset location.

Figure 7: Comparison of displacement fields on the outer faces of the region of interest. Top: VDIC data, bottom: FEM results.

The unique aspect of the DVC technique is that it provides quantitative deformation behavior throughout the volume of the specimen. Surface behavior, or near surface behavior as shown in Figure 7, can be measured through 2D DIC, 3D DIC, or a variety of other full-field deformation techniques. Therefore, selected internal strain distributions are presented in Figures 8-10 to show compare model data to the measurements. In these images, the modeled results are shown with the top layer of 90° cords removed for visibility. The color scale between modeled and experimental results is the same for the respective strain components.

In all three strain components, it is evident that the cords heavily influence the behavior, as would be expected. Qualitatively the predicted behavior is quite close to the measured behavior. One exception to this is visible in Figure 8 where the predicted load-direction strain in the vicinity of the 90° cords is significantly lower than that of the measured strains (see top edge of the plane Y=14.0mm

in Figure 8). It is believed that this is largely due to the lack of transverse flexibility in the modeled cords. It is likely that the actual nylon cords are not truly bonded together internally, thus the center of each cord acts similarly to a void with respect to transverse loading.

Figure 8: Strain (ϵ_{yy}) at $X=4.6$, $Y=14.0$, $Z=2.0$, and $Z=11.2$ mm for (a) the DVC and (b) the model results (top layer of 90° cords eliminated for visibility).

Figure 9: Shear strain (ϵ_{xy}) at $X=4.6$, $Y=14.0$, $Z=2.0$, and $Z=11.2$ mm for (a) the DVC and (b) the model results (top layer of 90° cords eliminated for visibility).

Figure 10: Shear strain (ϵ_{xz}) at $X=4.6$, $Y=14.0$, $Z=2.0$, and $Z=11.2$ mm for (a) the DVC and (b) the model results (top layer of 90° cords eliminated for visibility).

5 CONCLUSIONS

Digital volume correlation was applied to μ CT image sets of a tensile loaded rubber composite specimen. The specimen consisted of a silicon rubber matrix, sparsely reinforced with nylon cords. An internal contrast pattern in the rubber phase was obtained through the inclusion of glass microbeads and distributed voids. A series of baseline tests showed remarkably low levels of bias in strain under rigid body motions. The DVC results report great detail within the volume of the specimen, showing local and global influence of the nylon cords on the displacement and strain distributions. Modeling efforts using AFRL research software were conducted in an attempt to reproduce the DVC results. Qualitative and quantitative comparison between experimental and numerical displacements and strains shows very close agreement both globally and locally.

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